

Architectural Assurance of AI-based Driving Functions in Software-defined Vehicles

1st Sebastian Weber
FZI Research Center for
Information Technology
Karlsruhe, Germany
sebastian.weber@fzi.de

2nd Max Scheerer
FZI Research Center for
Information Technology
Karlsruhe, Germany
scheerer@fzi.de

3rd Thomas Weber
Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
Karlsruhe, Germany
thomas.weber@kit.edu

Abstract—With the ever-growing size and complexity of software used in vehicles, one differentiating factor perceivable for the user is the advanced functionality offered by AI-enabled software, e.g., emergency braking or lane keeping assistants. As always in the development of vehicles, safety is a paramount requirement for such software components. Analyses of the safety of such software components often rely on assumptions about the performance of the components and the usage of AI induces uncertainty, and the high resource demand of neural networks requires new forms of hardware components and system architectures. In addition, the development process of the software becomes more agile, requiring over-the-air updates and frequent analysis of compatibility and requirement fulfillment. To overcome the challenges arising from these developments regarding the analysis of AI-enabled systems, this paper proposes a new multi-level prediction system, that applies the concepts of model-based system engineering by employing architectural analysis and multi-level simulation. To gather the challenges stemming from these developments we reviewed the state of the art in the architectural analysis of AI-enabled systems in regard to safety and performance and how such systems can be assured and derived eight different challenges from them.

Index Terms—Architectural Assurance, Safety Analysis, Performance Analysis, Software-defined Vehicles, Safeguarding AI

I. INTRODUCTION

The automotive industry is undergoing a transformative phase, characterized by the advent of *Software-Defined Vehicles* (SDVs). This paradigm shift redefines the perspective of current hardware-defined vehicles to vehicles whose value creation is mainly defined by software. While the traditional user expectation of a vehicle was related to aspects such as mechanical performance, ergonomics or appearance, there is now a shift in this expectation towards software-provided functions that encompass features such as *Advanced Driver Assistance Systems* (ADAS), infotainment, connection to the cloud or new and upgraded functionality through over-the-air updates [1].

However, this shift towards SDVs and the use of software comes with several challenges such as safety, performance, security, more agile software development processes and continuous delivery. In this context, ADAS, which are designed to improve vehicle safety and driving comfort, play a crucial role. ADAS allow for a wide range of use cases, e.g.,

adaptive cruise control, lane-keeping assistance, automatic emergency braking, etc. These systems, however, rely on a complex interplay of sensors, vehicle control components, and complex processing components that commonly integrate AI-based methods such as *Deep Neural Networks* (DNNs), e.g., for pedestrian detection. Although AI introduces a lot of opportunities to realize a high degree of autonomy and sophisticated driving functions, it entails severe challenges in terms of safety. Virtually all AI-based driving functions implement DNNs from the field of deep learning. However, DNNs inherently exhibit a level of predictive uncertainty, which leads to situations where they produce incorrect predictions. Moreover, their black-box nature makes it nearly impossible to understand why such predictions have been made; even worse, the verification problem of DNNs is NP-complete [2] such that even relatively simple DNNs cannot be verified efficiently. Consequently, the assurance process of safety and performance of AI-based driving functions such as ADAS must begin as early as possible (i.e., at design-time) and be rigorously continued throughout the development process. In this context, a well-designed architecture is of paramount importance and must incorporate mechanisms such as redundancy or safety supervisors to deal with the uncertain nature of AI and to satisfy the safety requirements of the system.

The design process of AI-based driving functions involves numerous design decisions, which affect the system's quality attributes, however, their impact is difficult to assess before implementation. Traditionally, *Model-Based Systems Engineering* (MBSE) techniques are employed to analyze safety requirements qualitatively, i.e., they analyze whether the requirements are met or not. Furthermore, assuring safety requirements for systems containing AI components is an open research area where qualitative analysis is difficult to apply due to the unverifiable nature (in terms of prediction accuracy) of AI components. Ultimately, although there exist a series of works in terms of system safety analysis, they often neglect performance or hard real-time constraints. Especially for AI-based driving functions such as ADAS which process large amounts of data (e.g., perception systems), it is crucial to ensure that these processing systems meet certain real time constraints in order to make safe operational decisions [3]. To

be able to ensure this, we propose a new multi-level prediction system to enable the quantitative analysis of such systems by employing the concepts of MBSE in architectural analysis and multi-level simulation.

In section II, we review the state-of-the-art MBSE approaches for analyzing safety requirements and performance constraints of automotive systems. Hereby, we discuss both system level assurance approaches considering AI components and traditional approaches. Based on the state-of-the-art, in section III we elaborate and discuss open research directions and challenges in the face of architectural assurance of AI-based driving functions, which play a central role in the development of SDV systems. Discussing all possible directions and challenges, however, is beyond the scope of this paper; therefore, we focus exclusively on architectural analyses to quantitatively assess the safety requirements and performance of AI-based driving functions. Finally, in relation to the research directions we have discussed, we propose and discuss a framework for an architectural analysis of modeled AI-based driving functions to evaluate the impact of design decisions with respect to the safety requirements and performance constraints of the system in section IV.

II. STATE OF THE ART

In this section, we review state-of-the-art architectural analysis approaches in terms of safety and performance. Hereby, we do not exclusively focus on the automotive domain but also discuss approaches from related domains such as aerospace engineering, which are related regarding the safety requirements and analysis approaches. Moreover, we review analysis approaches that aim to safeguard AI-enabled systems; that is, systems that integrate at least one AI component. It is important to note that we use the term performance to describe the resources and time required for the execution of the system and its components, not the quality or accuracy of the results the system produces. Terms such as inference latency or inference time would convey the intended meaning of the term performance related to the AI components, but not related to the other non-AI parts of the system.

A. Architectural Analysis of Safety-Critical Systems

The very foundation of every architectural analysis approach is an *Architectural Description Language* (ADL). For the analysis of safety-critical systems, there are several ADLs that have proven successful for architectural analysis, namely the *The Architecture Analysis & Design Language* (AADL) [4], EAST-ADL [5], AUTOSAR [6], *Systems Modelling Language* (SysML) [7] and the *Modeling and Analysis of Real-Time Embedded Systems* (MARTE) [8]. While AADL is predominantly used in aerospace engineering, EAST-ADL and AUTOSAR can only be used to model automotive systems for which they were specifically designed; on the other hand, SysML and MARTE can be used domain-agnostically. Based on the ADLs, various safety and performance analyses can be conducted, which we discuss in the following sections.

1) *Safety*: In terms of MBSE and safety analysis, the most prevalent approaches are *Fault Tree Analysis* and *Failure Mode and Effects Analysis* (FMEA). Both aim to identify various failure modes that could potentially violate high-level safety requirements, provided that combinations of these failure modes are triggered. The two approaches differ in that fault tree analysis uses a top-down approach, starting with a specific undesirable event (linked to a safety requirement) and identifying the failure modes that could lead to this event, branching out to lower levels. On the other hand, FMEA follows a bottom-up approach, starting with low-level failure modes and examining how these could propagate to higher levels, ultimately affecting the safety requirement. Although fault tree analysis and FMEA reflect the predominant approaches for architectural safety analysis, other approaches such as *Simulation-based Verification* are also employed.

Regarding fault tree analysis and FMEA, there are many works, e.g., [9]–[13] which apply fault tree analysis or FMEA based on systems modelled with SysML. Because SysML is domain-agnostic, the applied approaches are not limited to automotive systems (e.g., [12]) but are also applied to other domains such as aerospace engineering (e.g., [10]). Similar approaches can be found in [14] and [15], [16] which all apply fault tree analysis or FMEA but differ only in the used ADL, i.e., [14] makes use of EAST-ADL and AUTOSAR domain models, and [15], [16] is based on systems modelled with AADL. The core idea of MBSE is to automatically translate the modelled system architecture (e.g., using SysML) into a safety model (e.g., a fault tree) because generating the safety models manually is a time-consuming and error-prone process [11]. This is typically achieved by using a dedicated error model to annotate the nominal system or architecture model with errors on the basis of which a fault tree is generated (e.g., [10], [16]). Also prominent in this context is the use of a failure synthesis tool environment such as HiP-HOPS [17] or AltaRica [18] for the qualitative analysis of error annotated system models. In order to determine whether safety requirements are violated, minimal cut sets are calculated or model checking is applied, returning the minimum sets (or combinations) of errors for which the safety requirement is violated. Beside fault tree analysis and FMEA, there are approaches such as described by Weissnegger et al. [19] which applies simulation-based verification techniques to EAST-ADL modelled systems for analysis.

2) *Performance and Real-Time Constraints*: Many approaches for the prediction of performance of AI-based components are employed in the context of neural architecture search (NAS). The goal of NAS is to automatically find the most suitable neural architecture for a specific task based on constraints, e.g., inference time or resource demand. She et al. [20] present their “hardware-aware prediction method based on double feature embedding (HADE)”. The authors apply unified node vectorization to represent the features of the neural network as a directed acyclic computation graph, which is updated according to a newly proposed double feature embedding. Based on these results, the last step executes

a resource aware latency prediction. The tool “DNNPerf” from Gao et al. [21] encodes the DNN as a graph, derived by an attention-based node-edge encoder. The performance-related factors are encoded as node and edge features, and the inference time is predicted by a trained graph neural network. In contrast, Wu et al. [22] characterize a model through the key operators it uses during model inference and the resource sensitivity curves of them. Both key operators and resource curves were researched for a range of 30 models and used to construct a tree data structure to aid the search of configuration candidates in the configuration space of the models. The tool “MAPLE” from Abbasi et al. [23] characterizes the hardware the model is executed on by measuring metrics and deriving a hardware descriptor from them. Together with the model architecture, this information is used to predict the model inference time with a trained regression model. The tool “nn-Meter” developed by Zhang et al. [24] predicts the performance of DNN model inference time on different hardware devices. Their approach automatically detects execution units on a device called kernels and uses adaptive sampling to determine which configurations of the configuration space to sample to build their latency predictors. Kong and Hong [25] use statistical information to predict the model inference time of AI-based object detection to determine an optimal offloading strategy between different hardware components with different model inference times and communication protocols. Similarly, Lu and Lyu [26] use a dataset collected during their research to train different models that can predict the model inference time of different variants of a MobileNetV3 and evaluate the accuracy of the prediction results of the different models. Li et al. [27] propose their framework “Edgent” for the partitioning of a DNN between device and edge according to an adaptive offloading strategy. They train a regression model for the model inference time prediction of the different model layers based on profiling results. The “latency estimation tool for investigation (LETI)” from Ponomarev et al. [28] employs a regression model trained on data gathered from different target devices with mobile GPUs. Kaufman et al. [29] present a learned model for tensor processing units and tensor computation graph programs. In addition, the authors employ their learned model in a XLA autotuner to discover faster programs. The tool “PALEO” from Qi et al. [30] uses an analytical performance model based on computation and communication time inside the model. The factors influencing both are derived from the model architecture and hardware configuration.

The scope of the review of state-of-the-art architectural analysis approaches in terms of performance in this section presented above is limited to the prediction of performance of AI-enabled systems. Therefore, we do not cover the usage of AI to predict the runtime of systems without AI-components, e.g., as described by Hutter et al. [31] in their survey. Instead, we have focused on analysis tools that have been or can be employed for the performance prediction of AI-enabled systems, either to predict the performance of such systems or to aid in the selection of a specific network architecture for the

AI-component. We also do not consider the learning process of AI components and constraints that can be applied there, e.g., like Metta et al. [32] in their case study on a multi-agent robot control system for the game air hockey or Dube et al. [33] for automated machine learning models. The fulfillment of real-time constraints is an important subarea of performance, and it has a close connection to the other considered quality attribute safety. Therefore, we specifically mentioned it as goal together with performance. Because the fulfillment of real-time constraints can be analyzed based on a general performance prediction, the reviewed state of the art does not consider it in particular.

B. Assurance of AI-based Systems

The architectural assurance of AI-based systems is an open and fairly challenging research field which can be attributed to various factors such as the high-dimensional input space (e.g., the pixel space in object detection tasks), the operating environment or the modelling of uncertainties (see Seshia et al. [34] for a detailed discussion). Although there are promising approaches, to our knowledge there is no approach that fully verifies safety requirements of AI-based system architectures.

Păsăreanu et al. [35] presents a compositional verification approach for autonomous systems with deep learning components. The authors build upon *Assume-Guarantee-Contracts* (AGCs) defined for each component of the system. AGCs define assumptions on the environment. If these are true, the system must satisfy the conditions defined in the guarantee part of the contract. Based on the AGCs of each subcomponent, the verification process of the entire system is decomposed into individual verification processes, which is generally known as *Compositional Verification*. More specifically, in such settings the AGCs for each component must be proven in isolation. Afterwards, the compatibility of the composition of the components is verified, considering the individual AGCs and the top-level safety requirement. The authors integrate AI components in the compositional verification approach by defining AGCs based on regions of the input space for which it could be proven that the DNN behaves correctly. Another approach is provided by Dreossi et al. [36], presenting a compositional falsification approach of cyber-physical systems with *Machine Learning* (ML) components. In their work, the system and AI component are abstracted to deal with the high-dimensional input space. The abstraction forms the foundation to conduct a compositional falsification procedure for detecting safety violations; that is, inputs for which an AI component produces incorrect predictions, leading to the violation of the system safety requirement. Assadi et al. [37] developed a quantitative notion of dependability assurance of learning enabled systems. They discuss assurance measures, quantifying the confidence of a learning enabled system that fulfills a specific dependability property at the system level. Similarly, Serban et al. [38] make use of Bayesian networks to analyze the uncertainty propagation of ML systems. Ultimately, [39], [40] describe an approach for analyzing the reliability of AI-enabled systems,

taking into account the predictive uncertainty of AI components. Moreover, the authors describe how an existing model-based reliability prediction approach is extended to evaluate architectural safeguards, e.g., architectural patterns (such as n-version redundancy) specifically designed to deal with AI-related uncertainties.

III. OPEN RESEARCH DIRECTIONS AND CHALLENGES

In the last section, we presented a representative overview of the state-of-the-art in terms of architectural safety and performance analysis of AI-enabled systems. The focus of our work is concerned with the assurance of AI-based driving functions from the perspective of safety and performance. We argue that especially the use of AI means that the current state-of-the-art approaches are no longer applicable and need to be extended. Therefore, we discuss open research directions and challenges that we have identified in connection with the architectural assurance of AI-based driving functions in SDVs. We argue that these challenges are not sufficiently covered by the current state-of-the-art. In particular, we identified three central research directions, namely (i) systematic integration of the predictive uncertainty of AI in MBSE, (ii) performance prediction of heterogeneous AI-enabled systems (iii) unification of semantically and abstractly distinct models. In the following, we elaborate challenges associated with each direction.

A. Systematic Integration of the Predictive Uncertainty of AI in MBSE

The verification of AI systems is a foundational and open problem in research [34]. Although there exist approaches for fully verifying neural networks in terms of robustness properties (e.g., [2]), these are only applicable to neural networks of small model capacity, making them impractical to apply even for comparatively simple DNNs (such as object detection). In terms of MBSE, this limitation is fairly problematic because most MBSE approaches aim to provide qualitative analysis of safety requirements. Therefore, we formulate the first challenge:

(C1) Assuring system-level safety requirements of advanced driving functions for SDVs based on unverifiable DNN.

Note that the term “unverifiable” is not entirely accurate because DNNs are in fact verifiable in terms of certain properties. The verification procedures, however, lack efficiency, making DNNs practically unverifiable. Consequently, analyzing safety requirements of AI-based driving functions qualitatively (in the sense of MBSE) is difficult to achieve. Instead, we argue that safety requirements should be analyzed from a quantitative or probabilistic perspective, i.e., by determining the probability of observing safety requirement violations such as discussed in [37]. This requires the predictive uncertainty of AI components to be systematically integrated into current (quantitative) MBSE approaches.

Seshia et al. [34] pointed out in their work that modeling the environment (in which the DNN is operating) and the DNN itself is fairly challenging due to numerous reasons (e.g.,

modeling of the system context, the high-dimensional input space of DNNs or the number of unknown variables of the environment). In terms of assuring AI-based driving functions, MBSE is facing the very same problems, leading to the second challenge:

(C2) Modeling and abstracting the environment of AI components to enable quantitative analysis of safety requirements.

One of the central drawbacks of DNNs is the inability to determine whether a certain prediction is correct or incorrect. It is challenging to understand how incorrect predictions affect the functionality of the remaining components of the system. Therefore, we formulate the third challenge:

(C3) Analyzing the error propagation of incorrect predictions to detect safety requirement violations.

In some cases, an incorrect prediction has no consequences, e.g., if the distance to the next vehicle is relatively large in automatic braking systems, it does not matter if the DNN-based object recognition component does not recognize the next vehicle ahead. In other cases, an incorrect prediction is likely to produce errors in the components depending on it, leading to cascading errors and the violation of safety requirements. This is aggravated by the predictive uncertainty of DNNs, where the process of observing correct or incorrect predictions is probabilistic. From the MBSE perspective, this means considering not only the propagation of incorrect predictions in the safety analysis, but also the circumstances or environmental conditions that are responsible for them.

B. Performance Prediction of Heterogeneous AI-enabled Systems

While performance prediction in MBSE has been researched for more than 30 years with various techniques [41], the performance prediction of AI-enabled systems is a rather new field of research [42]. The research reviewed in section II-A2 shows that the prediction approaches are tailored to specific model architectures and hardware specifications. While these approaches may be applicable to some DNNs employed in AI-enabled systems, they cannot cover the extent to which different DNNs and hardware will be used in software-defined vehicles in the future. An ADAS can be composed of multiple different DNNs deployed on a multitude of hardware components throughout the vehicle, which makes it nearly impossible to develop a single performance prediction approach to cover all variants and versions, even for one manufacturer. In addition, the existing approaches are focused on the prediction of the model inference time of single AI components, not AI-enabled systems consisting of AI and non-AI components. The prediction approaches based on DNNs trained on performance data gathered from a system could be adapted to predict the performance of a complete system, but the applicability of such an approach would be quite narrow. Even comparably small changes in the hardware architecture, e.g., switching from one original equipment manufacturer (OEM) to another with a slightly changed hardware component, could lead to

substantial performance differences. Instead of developing additional approaches with narrow applicability or extending existing ones, we state the fourth challenge:

(C4) Integrate existing model inference time and model-based performance prediction approaches into a framework.

The prediction of performance can be done on different levels of abstraction and based on different concepts, e.g., as presented in II-A2 by characterizing a DNN based on execution units like Zhang et al. [24] or key operators like Wu et al. [22]. Each chosen concept and level of abstraction has different properties regarding the trade-off between analysis runtime and result accuracy. The heterogeneity of AI-enabled systems in the context of software-defined vehicles makes it hard to determine one level of abstraction for the whole system. While the lowest required level could be chosen for the whole system, this would result in a high analysis time that could hinder the efficient and frequent analysis of the system. Therefore, we see the fifth challenge:

(C5) Analyse the performance of components of AI-enabled systems on the most suitable level of abstraction.

When analyzing systems on different levels of abstraction, a common criterion to switch between different levels is a defined region of interest either in the software or the hardware of the system, e.g., when a certain component or function is simulated. To be able to dynamically switch between different levels as explained by Ghosh [43], the simulated system state of the running analysis should be transferred to the subsequent analysis. While this is feasible when the level of abstraction is increased, so less detail is required for the following analysis, decreasing the level of abstraction is difficult. In addition, the model inference prediction approaches presented in II-A2 mostly rely on trained DNNs themselves, which do not expose a notion of a system state as output, and it is highly unlikely that it is possible to generate a current system state from the state of the prediction model. The sixth challenge therefore specifically addresses the usage of DNN-based performance prediction approaches into an analysis approach supporting different levels of abstraction.

(C6) Generate a simulated system state when using DNN-based performance prediction approaches.

C. Unification of Semantically and Abstractly Distinct Models

In MBSE, various models and model types are involved, ranging from purely structural models (e.g., architecture models or fault tree models) to behavioral models such as state machines or Markov models. Moreover, each model belongs to a different level of abstraction and serves distinct purposes. When analyzing safety requirements, each model plays a specific role at a certain level of abstraction in the overall analysis process. As discussed in section II, there are plenty of works that combine ADLs and error models to automatically generate fault trees for qualitative analysis of safety requirements; however, as already pointed out in section III-A, qualitative analyses are difficult to apply when DNN components are involved. Additionally, some systems require a fairly

hierarchical structure of models, starting at a high abstraction level which describes the central components of the system. Some of them require further refinements (i.e., they consist internally of further subcomponents). In such cases, the safety analysis is decomposed by analyzing each component and each subcomponent individually, forming a deep hierarchical structure (also known as hierarchical modeling [44]). This process might even involve different teams responsible for the analysis of each component. It becomes even more difficult if the assurance process involves multiple quality attributes such as proposed in this paper (recall that we aim to analyze performance constraints and safety properties/requirements). This introduces an even broader and heterogeneous landscape of semantically and abstractly different models. Consequently, we see the following central challenge:

(C7) Unifying semantically and abstractly different models and model types into a unified assurance framework.

Depending on the level of abstraction, the different modeling approaches and analysis tools use assumptions about the system they are modeling. While each model and tool itself requires these assumptions to be able to analyze the system, the combination of multiple models and tools on different levels of abstraction can allow for the validation of such assumptions. As an example, a modeling paradigm might use discrete time steps of fixed length to describe the behavior of the system. The corresponding analysis tool might not support validation of whether the mapping of system functions to those time steps is valid, but another modeling paradigm and analysis tool aimed at performance prediction might be able to achieve this. The corresponding eighth challenge we see is:

(C8) Validate assumptions of modeling paradigms and analysis tools through other paradigms and tools on different levels of abstraction.

IV. ASSURANCE OF AI-BASED DRIVING FUNCTIONS

In this section, we discuss and share our initial ideas and thoughts to address each of the research directions and associated challenges. For better illustration, consider the following (simplified) safety requirement of a DNN-based automated braking system taken from [35]:

$$\varphi := G((x = red) \Rightarrow F_{T < 3s}(velocity = 0)) \quad (1)$$

The property is specified in linear temporal logic where G denotes the global operator, in which $G(\gamma)$ reads: For all future states, condition γ holds; F denotes the eventual operator, in which $F(\gamma)$ reads: condition γ will be eventually true in some future state. In words, safety requirement (1) states that for all situation where the traffic light is red (which is to be detected in input image x), then the velocity of the vehicle becomes eventually 0 within 3s. One of the primary objectives that we want to tackle is an architectural safety analysis, which allows evaluating quantitatively whether the safety requirement is sufficiently addressed by the designed architecture (we go into details in section IV-A). However, let us assume that we are able to prove safety requirement (1) (based on methods

discussed in section II-A1), there is still a hidden assumption in the requirement which can lead to its violation, namely latency or performance assumptions. More specifically, how do we know whether a system efficiently performs all processing steps such that the velocity of the vehicle becomes eventually 0 within 3s? That is to say, even if we can formally prove safety requirement (1), it remains unclear whether the system guarantees this performance constraint because the prove is purely functional and neglects other aspects such as the underlying hardware of the system, the size of the DNN or the amount of input data to be processed; however, these crucially affects the satisfaction of requirement (1). We discuss this issue in more detail in section IV-B.

Architecting a system that fulfills safety requirements as good as possible while also being performant leads to a goal conflict, because addressing safety requirements by architectural means often leads to a deterioration in performance and vice versa. For example, redundancy is a common approach for meeting safety requirements; at the same time, however, it potentially degrades the performance of the system or may require additional computing resources to keep its performance. Therefore, it is important to analyze the architecture from both perspectives to make proper trade-off decisions. We return to this topic in section IV-C where we propose a framework unifying the concepts of section IV-A and IV-B to make such trade-off decisions.

A. Architectural Analysis of Safety Requirements

In section III-A, we discussed three challenges related to the architectural assurance of DNN-based driving functions, mainly arising from the intensive use of DNNs. Hereby, the question arises, how the concepts of MBSE can be extended to integrate the predictive uncertainty of DNNs in the analysis process.

Basically, we suggest to build upon the core idea of MBSE which, in simplified terms, involves the following steps: (i) Defining the safety requirement, (ii) modeling of the system architecture and (iii) qualitatively analyzing the modelled system under the perspective of various errors. Stewart et al. [16] describe an approach in which, after steps (i) and (ii), the nominal behavior of the system has been verified. To this end, the authors used *Assume-Guarantee Contracts* (AGCs) for each system component, formally describing their behavior. Based on the AGC annotated system model, the top-level safety requirement is verified using (e.g.) model checking. Each AGC of a component includes assumptions about the input and guarantees on the output of the component, if the assumption is true. More formally, an AGC is defined by the triple $\langle A \rangle \langle C \rangle \langle G \rangle$ for component C where A defines the assumptions about the environment and G the guarantees, provided that A holds. Afterward, an error model is used to annotate and extend the AGCs with errors by defining how these errors change the output of a component such that the system can be analyzed in the presence of errors. A key advantage of using AGCs is the decomposition of the verification process into multiple and more manageable

verification problems, each of which can be solved by a suitable verification procedure (*Compositional Verification*). In the following, we outline how we aim to expand this core idea to address challenges (C1)-(C3).

Following a compositional verification approach based on AGCs requires a corresponding contract for each AI component that must be formally proven to ensure no safety requirement violations. Challenge (C1), however, states that DNNs are not efficiently verifiable, meaning that we can not prove its correctness. Therefore, we argue to probabilistically approach this problem; that is to say, instead of verifying whether our system satisfies safety requirement φ qualitatively (i.e., is satisfied or not), we verify it quantitatively. In this case, the probability (or probability bound) that our system satisfies φ is determined, i.e., $Pr(\varphi)$. This requires the generalization of AGCs to stochastic AGCs [45] in which each assumption and guarantee is expanded with a respective probability bound, i.e., $\langle A \rangle_{\geq p_A} \langle C \rangle \langle G \rangle_{\geq p_G}$ which reads: Whenever A is satisfied with probability at least p_A , then component C satisfies G with probability at least p_G . Having stochastic AGCs eliminate the additional burden to verify the correctness of AI components; instead they are assessed quantitatively, which is much more in line with their probabilistic nature. Concretely, stochastic AGCs may include conditions or environmental variables under which we assume that the DNN produces incorrect predictions more likely. For example, if we assume to observe in 80% of the images no sensor noise, we expect the DNN to produce in 90% a correct prediction.

Considering environmental variables in the AGC of an AI component is directly related to challenge (C2). As pointed out in challenge (C2), modeling and abstracting the operating environment of DNNs in the context of automotive systems is a challenging endeavor, as the physical environment of such systems encompasses various physical elements and interactions. In previous work [39], [40], we described a Bayesian modeling approach to capture the environment of AI components by focusing only on the events that are likely to produce incorrect predictions of a DNN, i.e., such as increased brightness in an input image or sensor noise. These environmental variables are related to the predictive uncertainty of an AI component, forming a probabilistic model (which is complemented by a sensitivity analysis and additional domain knowledge, see [39], [40]). The model, in turn, can be queried from various points of view such as the occurrence of certain environmental variables (e.g., how likely are sensor errors or brightness variations in an image) and how they affect the predictive uncertainty (e.g., what is the probability that incorrect predictions are made in such scenarios). Having now a stochastic AGC $\langle A \rangle_{\geq p_A} \langle C \rangle \langle G \rangle_{\geq p_G}$ for some AI component C , we can determine whether the bounds p_A and p_G are satisfied by querying the probabilistic model of AI component C .

Ultimately, the challenge of analyzing the error propagation of incorrect predictions (i.e., (C3)) remains. According to Stewart et al. [16], including errors in the AGC or specifying how they affect the output of the component (as discussed

before) leads to implicit error propagation, since changing the output of one component may affect the input of another component and so forth; this directly addresses challenge (C3). Consequently, the mere use of AGC reasoning in combination with error modeling enables examining how other components are affected by incorrect predictions, which is manifested in the quantitative analysis of the corresponding AGC.

B. Architectural Analysis of Performance/Time Constraints

We discussed three challenges (C4), (C5) and (C6) related to the performance prediction of AI-enabled systems in III-B. The first two (C4) and (C5) mostly stem from narrow applicability of existing prediction approaches and the heterogeneity of AI-enabled systems. To meet these challenges, we propose the usage of the concept of multi-level simulation as described by Ghosh [43]. Multi-level simulation uses models and analyses on different levels of abstraction to achieve a simulation on the most suitable level of abstraction. When modeling and analyzing a system, the level of abstraction determines in most cases the runtime of the analysis and the accuracy it can achieve. The higher the level of abstraction, i.e., the more abstract the model and analysis are, the lower the runtime and accuracy of the results. We outlined an approach encompassing multi-level simulation to meet the challenges (C4) and (C5) independently of AI and AI-enabled systems as a plan for a prototype in [46] and the general concept in [47]. In the following, we describe how our approach can be applied for the multi-level simulation of AI-enabled systems to meet challenge (C6). The main focus here is to present the concept and share initial ideas on how to solve challenge (C6) to be able to use DNN-based prediction approaches in our prototype. This allows us to support the validation of assumptions regarding performance of AI-enabled systems that other simulators require for their results to be adequate to address challenge (C8) as outlined in the example in IV.

We base our approach on the concept of software performance engineering as outlined by Balsamo et al. in their survey on model-based performance prediction [41]. Therefore, we use a software and a system execution model, as proposed by Williams and Smith [48]. The software execution model contains descriptions of the workload scenarios, functional components of the software, and the control flow between those functional components, e.g., a software architecture and a model of the system usage. Because we want to support the performance prediction of AI-enabled systems, software components might use or be based on AI. Therefore, the workload scenarios include information like input size or other relevant properties. The simulation of the software execution model computes which software component has to be simulated at which point in time and the input parameters to be used. This information is necessary for simulating the system execution model, which takes additional information into account, namely the hardware and deployment of the software on this hardware. The result of this simulation is the performance prediction for the system we aim for.

The different levels of abstraction our multi-level simulation approach supports are in regard to the system execution model. Based on the results of the software execution model simulation, the most suitable system execution model and simulator can be determined. The decision for a specific level of abstraction can be either static or dynamic [43]. When the decision is made statically, all involved models and simulators are predefined before the simulation is executed. A dynamic decision on the other hand means that the following model and simulator are determined during a simulation execution.

Whenever our approach switches between different simulators, it generates an initial state of the simulated system for the following simulator. The inference model prediction approaches presented in II-A2 are possible candidates that could be used as simulators in our approach. The main obstacle to apply the concept of multi-level simulation is that these simulators do not have a notion of a simulated system state and therefore cannot be used as source to generate the initial states as stated in challenge (C6). To overcome this, we proposed the usage of a functional simulator that is executed in parallel to the prediction approaches [47]. The functional simulator correctly predicts the simulated system state, but not the time, and the prediction approaches can be provided with the initial state to improve the prediction accuracy.

C. Multi-Level Prediction Systems

As previously discussed, the assurance process of DNN-based driving functions must not be limited to safety analyses but also take into account performance constraints. Therefore, we envision an analysis framework that unifies the concepts discussed in the previous two sections which we refer to as *Multi-Level Prediction System (MLPS)*.

As pointed out in challenge (C7), this requires the unification of models and model types that differ in their semantics and level of abstraction. If we recall the concepts introduced in sections IV-A and IV-B, we can see that both are based on an architecture model, forming the starting point for each analysis, and a series of lower-level models, which are arranged hierarchically and required for each individual analysis. This generic structure can be extracted and unified into a single framework, providing a set of overarching analyses (or in our case two analyses, namely safety and performance analyses). Each of which is associated with a set of lower-level models, required to perform the specific analysis. The structuring of models into a hierarchy is also denoted as *Hierarchical Modeling* [44].

Based on hierarchical models, a generic analysis procedure can be implemented that performs the analysis by traversing the model hierarchy and invoking a corresponding analysis procedure. Depending on the overarching analysis, the traversal of the hierarchy can be either forwards (starting from top of the hierarchy down to the lower level models), backwards (starting with the lower level models and working its way up the hierarchy) or combination of both. To resolve the traversal direction, so-called *Import Graphs* [44] can be used, determining the order of the models to be analyzed.

Regarding the architectural safety analysis from section IV-A, for instance, the import graph is traversed backwards because the analysis is performed according to the principles of compositional verification (where the verification process decomposes into multiple verification problems that must be verified individually to perform the overall verification). Recall that we rely on AGCs linked with each system component. For simplicity, we assume that each AGC can be proven by analyzing a corresponding fault tree. Assuming that we have a hierarchy of fault tree models (where faults of a higher level are refined by fault trees of a lower level), the algorithm starts by analyzing the lower level models and works its way up the hierarchy. For this purpose, an analysis procedure such as [49] is invoked for each fault tree until the traversal algorithm has run through the entire import graph. From this point onwards, all AGCs are ideally correctly verified (otherwise the procedure terminates), so that the architecture analysis (using probabilistic model checking) can be performed as described in section IV-A.

The modeling and analysis of performance can be conducted similarly. The system and its components are modeled on different levels of abstraction and can be hierarchically structured according to the parts of the system they model. Instead of traversing the import graph backwards, it is traversed based on the decisions which level of abstraction is most suitable for which part of the system. Therefore, it is either decided statically to use a specific model and analysis for a specific part of the system or this switch is dynamically triggered through a condition. The goal is to not fully traverse the graph, but instead only traverse it as necessary to achieve the required accuracy.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we outlined various concepts on the architectural assurance of DNN-based driving functions in SDVs. First, we provided an overview of the state-of-the-art by reviewing a representative selection of scientific works of safety and performance analyses in the context of automotive systems, complemented by a discussion of works for assuring AI-based systems. Afterward, we discussed several research directions and associated challenges, predominantly resulting from the intensive use of AI and which are currently not sufficiently covered by the state-of-the-art. Finally, we outlined various concepts, complementing the state-of-the-art to address the challenges we identified. Hereby, we argued that the assurance process must not only encompass the analysis of safety requirements but also account for performance constraints which are implicitly required. In future work, we want to examine the research directions and challenges we have identified in terms of their completeness. To this end, we plan to implement the concepts we have developed based on an existing ADAS case study in order to iteratively re-evaluate and refine them.

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